

THE SPECIAL PLACE AND ESSENCE OF HABIB SADULLA'S POETRY IN CLASSICAL LITERATURE

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Abstract: A general classification of Habib Sa'dulla's classic poems is given in this article.

Keywords: classical literature, ghazal, rubai, simile, metaphor, poetry.

ОСОБОЕ МЕСТО И СУЩНОСТЬ ПОЭЗИИ ХАБИБА САДУЛЛЫ В КЛАССИЧЕСКОЙ ЛИТЕРАТУРЕ

Аннотация: В статье дана общая классификация классических стихотворений Хабиба Садуллы.

Ключевые слова: классическая литература, газель, рубай, сравнение, метафора, поэзия.

INTRODUCTION

It is commendable that Habib Sa'dulla, the real son of Namangan, used his pen in almost all areas of poetry and won the hearts of his fans in all directions. Especially if we focus on the place of Habib Sadulla in classical literature, if you read his ghazals full of similes and metaphors, rich rubai's with any poetry, your love for Uzbek classical literature will increase even more.

MAIN PART

Let's get acquainted with the classification of some ghazals and rubai's below:

I would say that there is a lot of trouble between us.

That's enough, let's talk openly.

Unbeknownst to me, one day it came out of my mouth,

A drum rang in every ear.

It was a delicate matter, actually,

Every mouth swelled, poor thing.

The earth turns you white,

Don't do us, it's a dirty word.

What a wonder, what a weapon

My lover's tongue is sadpora talk.

It was a sacred gem when it was in the heart,

When he spoke, he talked a lot.

I wrote "Speech" as a speaker,

Now there is a lot of trouble between us.

From the beginning to the end of the ghazal, the poet remembers some of the shortcomings of humanity.

I would say that there is a lot of trouble between us.

That's enough, let's talk openly.

the poet says that what the poet said to one of the two lovers on the condition that they "stay between us" was leaked by a friend who did not know how to keep a secret. Of course, keeping a secret is one of the human abilities, and its absence is one of the disadvantages. Flaws are more characteristic of human nature than abilities.

Unbeknownst to me, one day it came out of my mouth,

A drum rang in every ear.

The words spoken in confidence to Yor come out of his dahan, that is, his mouth, and become like the sound of a drum ringing in every ear among the crowd interested in the conversation. The poet pointed to one of the human shortcomings in this very place. We all know that when the human race hears something very interesting, they want to tell it to someone else and become a "hero". Well, if it does not destroy the purity of information among people, this statement does not cause too much concern to the owner. However, when the matter is hot in everyone's mouth, people mix their own information with the real information and add ten together.

It was a delicate matter, actually,
Every mouth swelled, poor thing.

Yes, it is. The poet continues the ghazal with the above thought. Here, the word "delicate" can mean that the sentence is delicate for the owner of the heart, or that the sentence is short but meaningful. People fill that delicate sentence or short sentence with tissue, inflate it artificially, convey it to each other, and make it sound.

The earth turns you white,
Don't do us, it's a dirty word.

When the word spreads among the people, after it is enriched with the necessary lies, it will certainly not go beyond causing anger for saying that word. And the one who could not keep that secret properly can leave the right position.

What a wonder, what a weapon
My lover's tongue is sadpora talk.
It was a sacred gem when it was in the heart,
When he spoke, he talked a lot.

It will be appropriate if we recall a famous Turkish proverb right here. "A secret that two people know is not a secret." A word has the same value as a secret. If the poet wanted everyone to know the story, he could have told it to the people in the bazaars and stalls. If this deposit gets out, it will be a great weapon for the owner of the secret. That is why it is beneficial for those who have a heart, whether it is their own or someone else's, to keep speech as a sacred treasure in their heart. In addition, the sentence has not only a secret feature, but also a confirmation feature. It is a praiseworthy thing that the affirmation of that love remains a sacred gem in the heart. When it is spoken, when it reaches strangers, it is sure to cause problems like above.

I wrote "Speech" as a speaker,
Now there is a lot of trouble between us.

The poet ends the poem in a wonderful way. As an eloquent speaker, the poet is telling the lover of poetry what the consequences will be if the lover's secret is passed from one heart to another and goes beyond the language. And, of course, he ends the last verses of the ghazal in the same way as at the beginning. This, of course, is a unique poetic method in classical literature, which adds beauty to the charm of the ghazal.

Habib Sa'dulla is remembered by students as a patriotic person through his Rubai's.
My heart is filled with love for the Motherland,
You have tuned your heart to sing faithfully.
If my voice goes wrong when I sing
This song is called Watan and has been tuned.

In this Rubai, it is clear that in the heart of the famous poet, the love of the country is at a high level, and in general, there is a cry called "sing loyalty to the country" in his language. He is saying to sing the love of the country with all his voice.

I was born with a sweet tongue, habib,
I have a pure and open heart, habib.
I opened my mouth and put glue on it
That's how I got there myself.

CONCLUSION

This is one of the Rubaiyats written in the spirit of patriotism. Like everyone else, the poet loved beautiful songs and sweet words like his mother's since he was born, he felt and loved open and pure hearts, and after placing the love of the country in his heart as the ultimate goal, he became known as the "singer of the country", Habib Sadulla. brings what is known.

References

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